

Chapel of Grace, Ile-Ife

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Language, Christianity, English

The Chapel of Grace, Ile-Ife started as a fellowship of Christian staff of the University of Ife Teaching Hospital now The Chapel of Grace, Ile-Ife started as a fellowship of Christian staff of the University of Ife Teaching Hospital now Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, Ile-Ife. A group of the members of staff of the Teaching Hospital who began to meet to share their Christian faith and conviction decided to organise themselves into a fellowship in the late 1980s. In the early days of the fellowship, they got the leave of the hospital management to meet at a suitable venue within the engineering yard of the Ife hospital unit. From this venue they moved to their permanent site about fifty meters from the second gate of the Ife hospital unit of the hospital. The church is led by a church council comprising of the senior pastor, other pastors, members of the deaconate, leaders of the various arms of the church as well as other eminent members of the Christian community in Ile-Ife. The council meets annually or when it becomes necessary to take important decisions for the progress of the church. Next to the church council is the pastoral board which meets more regularly to plan the activities of the church and provide leadership for the members. There are several activity groups within the church which members are encouraged to join to achieve the set goals for which the ministry was started. Membership of the church comprises mainly of the working population of the hospital. The nature of the hospital is such that many of the staff undertake various training programmes to specialise in their desired field of medical and health practice. Many of these individuals worship at the Chapel of Grace during their training and relocate to other towns and cities to settle and practice as professionals. The church has had a highly mobile population over the years. Although several staff settle in permanent jobs in the hospital and continue in the church. They are joined by others who work outside the hospital community but are delighted to identify with the church. The church's most celebrated annual programme is the "Power in the Word Conference". It is a programme where the word of God (the bible) is dissected and taught passionately. Other annual programmes which the church holds include Choir Anniversary, Blissful Home Seminar, a carol at Christmas and special programmes for children, youths, men and women respectively. Aside the annual programmes, the church meets every Sunday for the Sunday worship service and on Wednesday (weekly programme for bible exposition/teaching and prayers). The church holds a prayer vigil on the last Friday of the month as well as a prayer meeting before the commencement of work every Monday morning. The church in collaboration with the hospital community organises prayers a couple times each year specifically for the peace, progress and development of the hospital.

Date Range: 1989 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria

Region tags: Ile-Ife, Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria

Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Authorised King James version of the Bible
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCcCRIVrfJJRYGRI3eG3ukCA/about>
- Source 1 Description: Chapel of Grace youtube account

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/>
- Source 1 Description: The Holy Bible

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The church is located within the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital. It was established by a section of the Christian staff of the hospital. The mosque which serves the Muslim community of the hospital is located to its immediate left. Besides this mosque, the church also interacts with other religious groups in the ancient city of Ile-Ife.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The church engages in proselytising and seeks to expand the membership through evangelism.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The church accommodates plurality of religious beliefs. It is in a town where the African Traditional Religious groups are found in their numbers.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Though the church actively proselytises, it does not disparage members of other faiths in its environment neither does it seek to increase its membership by violence or by intimidating people of other faith groups.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: There are no violent conflicts between religious groups in the sample region. The various religious groups domiciled in the sample region demonstrate their willingness to co-exist peacefully in the sample region.

- ↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):
 - No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:
– Yes

- ↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):
 - No

Notes: Birth only confers attendance at the church on children born to parents who identify as members of the church. Such children are however at liberty to choose to continue worshipping at the church when they become adults.

- ↳ Assigned by personal choice:
 - Yes

Notes: The church allows adults who are persuaded about their membership of the group to take the decision to join them when they feel ready to do so.

- ↳ Assigned by class:
 - No

Notes: Though many of the congregants are members of the hospital community, those who have no links with the hospital identify with the group. A sizeable number of the members are health professionals like doctors, nurses, pharmacists, administrators, accountants, radiographers, laboratory scientists, optometrists etc who work in the hospital. This class of members is closely followed by staff of the Obafemi Awolowo University and others living in the town who freely decided to join the group.

- ↳ Assigned at a specific age:
 - No

Notes: There are no specific age barriers to the church membership. The general idea is that full membership is accorded any adult who identifies with the ideals of the group and willing to abide by the guiding philosophy of the church.

- ↳ Assigned by gender:
 - No

- ↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: To be accorded full membership, intending members are required to undergo a few weeks of bible study classes which encapsulate the teachings and core biblical beliefs of the church. This is usually concluded within two months with an hour of bible exposition every Sunday morning. Before finally accorded full membership status, those who have not undergone baptism are encouraged to do so in the church while those who have done so in a bible believing group are exempt from doing so a second time.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The church engages in evangelism. According to the group, this is in strict adherence to the mandate given the believers by Jesus Christ.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Every member of the church is encouraged to participate in the evangelism either corporately or individually.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Though this cannot be said to be mandatory, however, members are encouraged to take part in missions. The church holds an annual medical outreach where all medical professionals in the church visit villages around the city to offer free medical services and also preach the gospel to the community. These outreaches have yielded tremendous results with branches of the church planted in a number of such communities around Ile-Ife.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: In actual sense, the church admits that it is possible for individuals to have identified with Christ for a period and such fellow recount their beliefs either verbally or in their actions. They do not become adversaries to such individuals. They keep praying for them and hopeful such would retrace their steps back into the fold of Christ.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 300

Notes: The current population of the Chapel of Grace stands at about 300 persons. However, by its composition and nature, the church has a highly mobile population. A significant size of its members are trainees undergoing different forms of health and clinical programmes and internship in the hospital. Some of them undergo training in medicine and surgery, nursing, pharmacy, physiotherapy, community health training programme, health information management etc. Others are interns, junior and senior medical professionals. They identify with and worship at the church during their training programme while many of them leave the town to seek job opportunities within and outside the country upon the completion of their training. Over the years, several hundreds of members have left the community but still continue to identify with the church in their various locations.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1

Notes: The sample region is quite a large population. Though the members are in their hundreds, they are still a small fraction of the sample region.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: Churches which identify as Pentecostals are prevalent in the sample region. Many of them, including the Chapel of Grace are independent of one other. However, they interact well among themselves and share resources and ideas to build one another up in their faith.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The church is well organised. It has a senior pastor, other supporting pastors, deacons and heads of units and departments among others.

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: The church establishes branches in villages around Ile-Ife. When such churches are established, members of the evangelism and outreach unit provide leadership for the established branches and continue to travel there each week. However, pastors get appointed for some of the branch churches who oversee the affairs of such branches. The pastors so appointed recognise the authority of the Chapel leadership in the hospital and submit to them in all things.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The pastoral board at one level takes decisions in furtherance of the church's objectives. However, the highest decision making organ is the church board which comprises of all pastors and other functionaries of the group. It meet at specified times to take far reaching decisions on the church.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 6

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: There is an involvement of the members and leaders in the appointment to leadership positions in the church. A couple of years ago when deacons were to be appointed, members were requested to submit names of those they recommended to serve in that capacity under confidential cover. This was processed further by the pastoral board before the new deacons were appointed.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: Registered members also known as workers or leaders may play some roles in choosing the leader of the church. However, the full responsibility of this rests with the pastoral board and the church council.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes in the power of prayers in determining such an important task as leadership recruitment. The leadership subjects themselves to periods of fasting and prayers when embarking on an important task of selecting or recruiting leaders.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders in the church are still considered as humans who are capable of making mistakes and committing errors.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Followers are not in the habit of looking out or shopping for the errors of their leaders though they believe that their leaders are not infallible.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: This is not a usual practice in the religious group. No leader at any level looks out for the errors or mistakes of other leaders.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: Political leaders do not usually interfere in the administration of the church although they have the powers to do so. The church has conducted itself in the most honourable way which effectively makes political leaders give its leaders the due regard to run the affairs of the church.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Though the followers or disciples of the leader hold them in high regards, they do not necessarily follow them blindly without considering the appropriateness of their pronouncements. However, the leaders have been found to be upright, well guided and balanced in their views. This makes the followers to keep faith with them over the years.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The religious group believes in the supremacy of the Holy Bible. They follow the its guidance and instructions on all matters of life and living.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that the Holy Bible is divinely inspired by God. They hold that He used angels and prophets to reveal His mind to humankind through the contents of the Holy Bible.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Their scriptures are fully canonised and cannot be altered under any guise.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Although the church encourages leaders to have some form of theological training which helps in their interpretation of the scriptures, they do not affirm that the interpretation of scriptures are the exclusive rights of leaders who have had any form of theological training.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: The bible which the church believes in has already been transmitted long time ago.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have monumental religious architecture. They have worship centres where they meet for meetings which are built decently to meet the needs of the congregation.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The church has a baptismal spot behind its worship centre within the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital. It is considered a sacred spot where they baptise those who have undergone the church discipleship programme and the baptismal class. Such members upon their baptism are considered full members of the church.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Members in the branches are encouraged to attend special programmes in the headquarter church in the hospital. In fact, the church usually provides free transportation to members attending the programmes.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: It is obligatory for leaders in the branches to attend or visit the headquarter church especially during important programmes. They may only be excused when there are obvious personal issues they need to attend to.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The church considers the spirit and body as distinct parts of humans though both are required to keep the human alive and functioning.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The church considers the spirit and the physical body as distinct components of the human essence. They hold that the body is like the vehicle/container through which the spirit conducts itself around. They see the body as that substance which gives the spirit the ability to perform that which it pleases.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The church holds that flesh and blood will not inherit eternal life but that the real essence of the human which is their spirit will live forever either in eternal bliss or eternal damnation.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that there is an afterlife after this current realm of existence

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that there are two locations of the afterlife. They believe that those who follow divine directions will live in eternal bliss in a realm above the earth while those who live in disobedience will endure so much pain and deprivation in Hades beneath the earth. It is a place of unquenching fire and suffering.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: The church is clear about the geographical position and space of the afterlife. Two of such afterlives are believed upon in the church. One is above and the other beneath. The one above is for saints with God and that beneath with Satan under very excruciating and painful conditions.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: The church conducts decent burial services for their deceased members. They also join members in burying their deceased family members who are not members of the church.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Burials for deceased members are conducted by the church in agreement with the wishes of either the dead or their family. If the dead or their family chooses for their departed

one to be interred in a cemetery, in their homes or compounds or other places, the church honours their desire and cooperates with them.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: This is not common in the church. However, the church may not deny anyone who wishes to be buried in such place in their homes their desires.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Notes: No other burial types are popular or practised among members of the Chapel of Grace, Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, Ile-Ife.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the existence of supernatural beings. They hold the good ones in high esteem but are in a constant spiritual battle with the evil ones.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high God is the head of all powers and principalities that exist. They believe that with His support, no evil powers can overcome them.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The church conceives the supreme high god as possessing human qualities like a mighty hand, eyes which see through the hidden places etc

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The church conceives the high god one as having his abode high up beyond the firmament

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The church never equates the supreme high god with any mortal. He is seen as the highest and greatest who has no equal.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The church sees all humans as the emanation of the high god. They conceive of all humans as creations of the high god and as the express image of the supreme being.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high God is seen by the church as possessing all good qualities and being able to bring every good promise he has made to his people to pass. He is benevolent, omnipotent, omnipresent and much more.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds the supreme high God as the creator of the universe and so they agree that as the creator, He has full knowledge of all that the world entails.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The church conceives of the supreme high god as an omnipotent and omnipresent being. Therefore, it follows that they hold him as having knowledge of all that there is in the entire universe.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The church belief the position of the bible which says that the eyes of the supreme high God runs through the whole earth beholding those who are perfect in their ways. They believe that the supreme high God sees both in the light and in the dark. In fact, they believe that as the Bible posits, darkness is as light before him.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: This religious group holds that even darkness is not dark to the supreme high God. This assertion is found in Psalms 139. He sees the motives of the heart and can tell exactly the manner of hidden motives each individual has.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The church holds that the world was created by the supreme being. It then follows that the supreme being has all knowledge of the world.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high God is the uncaused cause who makes all things happen in the world.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high God rewards all the deeds of mortal men and women. They hold that He gives a just reward for all their actions.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme being punishes all the wrong deeds of mortal men and women. They believe that He sees and punishes all evil deeds and leaves nothing out when visiting the iniquities of mortals.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high God has sovereignty over all and determines either directly or by other means the events and occurrences which take place among humans.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God is conceived as benevolent, kind, loving among other attributes among the members of this group.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that when the supreme high God is sorely provoked and has given enough time for repentance for wrongdoing, he could decide to discipline, punish or avenge the evil of humans who have exhausted his patience. He could also become angry and execute judgement on the disobedient.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Though the supreme high God does not possess hunger for food, he craves and earnestly longs or hungers for righteousness, holiness and good conduct.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high God is a jealous God who cannot endure the sharing of His glory with another being. He does not take kindly to anyone who worships any other being apart from Him. In fact, this is a commandment he gave to the ancient nation of Israel as part of their obligations to Him.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The features which the supreme high God exhibits are innumerable. Among other features, he is slow to wrath, merciful and graceful.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The method of divination which the church deploys in their interaction with the supreme being is prayers and invocation.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Though the church believes that religious specialists or leaders could assist fellow Christians in seeking the face of the supreme being, they believe that each Christian has an inalienable right to seek God themselves and obtain whatever they desire from him.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The church believes that the supreme high god communicates

with the living also through the scriptures.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: The church holds that previously human spirits do not inhabit the same earthly space or corridor with the living. They believe that once an individual dies, they vacate their earthly address and move to a new habitation having no direct contact with humans anymore.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The group acknowledges the existence of non-human supernatural beings. They believe that the supreme being has those who are members of His theocratic government while the devil also has those spirits he enlists in his business.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Except under special circumstances, the group holds that humans are incapable of seeing these non-human supernatural beings.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The group holds that the non-human supernatural beings have as much knowledge of the world as they are granted by the supreme being.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that their ability to see humans everywhere normally visible is subject to how much the supreme being grants them permission.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that their ability to see humans everywhere normally visible is subject to how much the supreme being grants them permission.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that their ability to see inside the heart/mind (hidden motives) is subject to how much the supreme being grants them permission

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that this ability of the non-human supernatural beings is subject to how much the supreme being grants them permission

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: This is subject to the permission granted them by the supernatural being.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Because they are divine entities, they possess the qualities of the supreme being. For example, they are not restricted or limited to a single location at a time unlike humans. They do not need to travel physically like humans. They can access a building or room even when all doors and windows are shut.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the deliberate causal efficacy which the non-human supernatural beings have derive from the supreme being. Without the supreme being, they can do nothing.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the reward which they dole out to humans are carried out as duties given to them by the supreme being.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the punishments which they dole out to humans are carried out as duties given to them by the supreme being.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that they can kick start the process of either rewarding or punishing humans for their action. They can do this without getting physically involved in the process but by orchestrating and setting the ball in motion for the reward or punishment.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They exhibit negative emotions when they need to punish the wrongs done by men/women who have been given opportunity to repent but failed to utilise their chances.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: They are held by the church for possessing hunger for apportioning rewards and punishments to deserving members of the human race.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Aside the features mentioned above, the church also believes that the supernatural being also exhibits other features. These include; being a dependable and impregnable shield and defence to those who trust him.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supernatural beings are organised hierarchically. For example, they believe that while there are angels, there are also arch angels who supervise the activities of angels under them.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Notes: The church holds that it is the prerogative of the supreme being to determine how and where to deploy the supernatural beings who make up his theocratic government. No strict domain is reserved for these beings though some of them are perceived as being deployed to carry out certain types of tasks. This does not mean they cannot be deployed at the instance of the supreme being to carry out other tasks outside of the categories which they have done in previous times.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that the supreme being carries out supernatural monitoring on

humans. They hold that the divine being watches humans for their adherence to divine instructions and that rewards and punishments await those who either choose to obey or disobey divine instructions.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Taboos are actions or deeds which are forbidden in the estimation of the church. They hold that sin is very condemnable and would attract punishment either sooner or later.

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that it is bad enough to commit sin but when humans choose to commit such sin in the environment of the church building, such action is seen as a double affront to the supreme being.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that humans are the spiritual temple of the supreme being. They therefore conceive of the human body as a sacred object where the supreme being dwells. That accounts for their stern stance against the use of the human body to commit any form of sin.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The church believes that supernatural beings care about every aspect of the lives of their members. So they encourage their members to always be mindful of this fact and act in such manner as would be acceptable by the supreme being and his supernatural agents.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that murder is a heinous crime which attracts God's severe punishment

on the perpetrator. They hold that no one is permitted to take the life of any other human being.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: The church holds that the supernatural being cares about sexual relations with animals (bestiality), premarital sexual acts and extra marital sexual engagements. They also hold that the supernatural being does not approve of sexual relations between people of same sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The church is of the firm belief that the supernatural being cares about every aspect of the lives of their members. This includes their fair treatment of all mortals, their kindness to their spouses and respect for all humans.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The church believes that the appropriation of supernatural punishment is

coordinated by the high god. It is however the prerogative of the high god to determine if the execution of supernatural punishment would be directly handled by him, any of his supernatural beings (agents) or by cause and effect principle.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that punitive measures meted out to members is to encourage obedience to divine instruction and to constantly remind them that there are consequences for every wrong action. This keeps them in remembrance of the demand on them to remain on track as their faith prescribes..

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that punishments in the afterlife would not end. Those who are consigned to punishment would live under the punishments for eternity.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that life itself is an unending battle. So when anyone comes under divine punishment, they may struggle to overcome normal challenges that they

encounter in their daily life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the forms of punishments available to those who disobey divine instructions is endless. While some people may die prematurely, others may be struck by very strange disasters like earthquakes, landslides etc

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church does not believe in reincarnation. However, it holds that rewards in this life and in the life to come are so numerous that no human can possibly conceive them in their totality. Some of the other rewards in the afterlife include highly melodious music, peace of mind, being in close proximity with the supreme being always etc.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that rewards in this life also includes miraculous deliverances from evil attacks, unmerited promotion at work, favour from men and from the supreme being among others.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The whereabouts of the messiah is known but his time of return to the earth is unknown

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes in Jesus Christ as their messiah. He is alive and identified

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: He came earlier about 2000 years ago and would return at an unspecified time in the future.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: The church holds that his coming is near. This believe has been held since he returned to the supernatural being some 2000 years ago. They still believe that he is returning soon. This 'soon' keeps being passed from one generation to the next.

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Notes: The church holds him as their only messiah.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Notes: The messiah has no other purpose aside the ones listed above.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the end will come after a series of events that will take place in the future. The people agree that there shall be wars and rumours of wars between the nations of the world, there shall be natural disasters and political instability among others. They say that when these begin to happen, they signify that the end is near. These signs, according to them would precede the eschaton.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: There is just one specific task which the members of the church are expected to perform in anticipation of the world's end. They are enjoined to keep preaching the good news of Jesus Christ. The purpose of this is that Christ had told Christians that until the gospel is preached to every tribe and nation, he would not return for the eschaton.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the eschaton will usher in theocracy (God's reign) on earth.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

- ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - Notes: Only a few are reckoned majority of whose identities are not known by the church would survive the eschaton.
- ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
- ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No
- ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other survival condition:
 - Yes [specify]: Those who will stand and not yield to the terrors of the anti-Christ will survive the eschaton.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes

- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: Though the church speaks well and is favourably disposed to grooming of beauty, it does emphasise the importance of good character over and above beauty which neglects good character. The group also encourages members to be assertive but also asks members to exhibit their assertiveness in areas that are acceptable to the supreme being and which will promote good conduct.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The church also encourages cooperation, understanding, fellowship with each other, sexual purity and sanctity of the marriage union etc.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: No other form of sexual partner is allowed for any male member of the church apart from their duly married partner. They are not allowed to have sexual relations with any other human or with an animal for that matter. Premarital sex is equally not permitted for any member of the church(male or female).

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: No other form of sexual partner is allowed for any female member of the church apart from their duly married partner. They are not allowed to have sexual relations with any other human or with an animal for that matter.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Members of the church do not consume alcohol or cigarette.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 12

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 48

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the government of their State and country.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: This is usually provided to students who have to travel from their hostels to church every Sunday.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: The church receives tithes from members who are willing to offer it.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government of the State and the country taxes the members of the church.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the Nigeria Police Force.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the judicial system of the State (Osun State) and country (Nigeria)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: This happens as an addition to prison terms for greivious offences in the country. However, no member of the church has ever been subject to such punishments. They are mostly well behaved and responsible citizens of the nation.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, This happens generally in the country if such property is established to have been fraudulently acquired or is established to be a proceed of crime. No member of the church has ever suffered this form of punishment, though.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Though most members are medical personnel, a few of them, their parents or children have enlisted as members of the Nigeria Military either as medical professionals in the force, as regular combatants or as other categories of workers within the Armed Forces .

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are protected by the Nigeria Military.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group adopts the English as well as the Yoruba language as modes of communication.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group adopts the use of the Gregorian calendar and their events and programmes are held in line with the dates on the Gregorian calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Group members buy their individual or family food needs from local markets and other food outlets.